

Guide to Episodic Trends Analysis

Šizling, A.L., V. Rineau and P. Pokorný. 202X. A novel method for palaeoecology, biogeography, archaeology and geology: analysis of small N data to detect episodic trends along timelines and spatial transects. **REF**

Content

Introduction	p. 5
Part 1: Analysis of Trend Episodes	p. 7
Utility ETA 01 - Indices	p. 9
Utility ETA 02: Global Trend	p. 16
Utility ETA 03: Sampling Effort	p. 20
Utility ETA 04: Detecting Episodic Trends	p. 23
Utility ETA 07: Combined Analysis	p. 29
Part 2: Calibration	p. 31
Main Idea	p. 33
Utility ETA 101: Generator	p. 34
Utility ETA 05: Link Data and Simulation	p. 42
Utility ETA 08: Calibration	p. 47
Frequently Asked Questions	p. 51

Introduction

The analysis introduced here has two distinct parts: (i) the analysis itself and (ii) its calibration. The first part provides information on the presence or absence of non-random diversity trends for each consecutive triple of sampling windows, as well as the most likely type of trend (Type T1-T5; see Fig. 3 in Šizling et al. 202X). The second part calibrates the probabilities of taxa (or industries or any other items) appearing (π_{App}) or disappearing (π_{Dis}) from the assemblage under analysis and explores the accuracy of the first part of the analysis with respect to the given sampling effort.

Both parts of the analysis detect non-random diversity trends in a sequence of assemblages by analysing data series. The required data for the analysis are: (i) lists of items (e.g., taxa, artifacts, individuals; the numbers of sampled specimens found in subsequent sampling windows, σ , are useful but not mandatory), (ii) the time span of each sampling window, and (iii) periods between consecutive sampling windows (for terminology, see Fig. 1 in Šizling et al., 202X). The required data for calibration are: (i) a depth-age model; (ii) minimum and maximum depths of each sampling window; and (iii) the number of sampled specimens for each taxon and assemblage. If these data are lacking, they can be arbitrarily defined the same for each sampling window.

See the section 'Practical Notes' for instructions on what to do when some required data are missing.

The method can be applied across a wide spectrum of scientific fields, each with its own terminology. For instance, in palynology, replace "taxon" with "pollen type" and "sample" with "pollen grain"; in paleontology, replace "taxon" with "genera" (or higher taxon) and "sample" with "fossil"; in archaeology, replace "taxon" with "type of industry, culture, or technology" and "sample" with "find" or "artefact".

Fig. 1 in Šizling et al. (202X) explains the terminology used here and may be helpful to the reader.

The method can be used to analyse both time and spatially defined data-series. For simplicity, we use the terminology of time-series; replace "time" with "space" when analyzing spatially defined series.

We also use years as basic units, but the user can use any time units (e.g., Myr) if used consistently throughout the analysis.

There are multiple files to handle during the analysis. For simplicity, all files are labeled as In_01 [free text].txt, In_02 [free text].txt, etc., or Out_01 [free text].txt, Out_02 [free text].txt, etc. Each of the two steps (analysis and calibration) requires running multiple utilities (ETA 01, ..., ETA 09). Only the three input files for the first utility (ETA 01) are labeled as inputs (In_01, In_02, In_03) and consist of raw data. The output from the first utility (ETA 01) is labeled as Out_01 and serves as an input to the subsequent utility (ETA 02), and so forth for all other utilities in sequence. The example files used in the case study (see main text) are provided along with the computational utilities.

There are multiple setting choices for each utility (ETA 01,..., ETA 09). The settings are preset to achieve the highest performance based on our experience with pollen data. Therefore, we do not recommend changing the settings for standard analyses, unless the test of performance using simulated assemblages shows low efficiency. The settings are explained in this MANUAL for each computational utility separately (see below).

The first line of each input file (In_01 [free text].txt, In_02 [free text].txt, In_03 [free text].txt) is a caption (free text), and the second line is the headline for the columns. Strings and numbers are separated by a tab space (code: #9). The file extension is '*.txt' in all cases.

Part 1

Analysis of Trend Episodes and Trend Types

Utility ETA 01 - Indices

The purpose of this utility is to prepare data for trend analysis. The utility computes the indices T , N , and G (Eq. 1-3 in Šizling et al., 202X) between all pairs of sampling windows from all consecutive triples of sampling windows. The results can be found in the file 'Out_01 [free text].txt'.

The Panel

Run the utility: (i) load In_01; (ii-optional) load In_02; (iii) load In_03; (iv) create Out_01; (v-optional) create Out_00; (vi) press 'RUN'. The end of the computation is indicated by a pop-up window displaying the message 'END' on your screen.

The Files on the Input

File In_01 [free text].txt; required

(details on Samples)

```

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

```

Details on Samples (In_01) – **Velké ohbí** – Observed

Sequence Code	Sample Code	Reference Point	Specimens (sigma)	Span
10	1	684 895	81.85	
10	2	847 992	88.35	
10	3	1037 1251	94.975	
11	1	505 800	50	

...

```

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

```

The first line is free text, which is mandatory; otherwise, the first data line will not be processed. 'Velké ohbí' is the name of the site analysed.

Sequence Code (type: integer): An identifier for the data-series (site, core, locality, etc.). Data with different Sequence Codes are analysed separately. For example, if there are two Sequence Codes in the 'In_01' file (e.g., Sequence Code=2 and Sequence Code=3), the utility will run two independent analyses. If there is a need to analyse all sites together (e.g., a global analysis using data from multiple continents), all data lines must have the same site code (the site code for the one global site to analyse).

Sample Code (type: integer): An identifier for the sampling window within the site code. There is no need to assign smaller or larger Sample Code to older or earlier windows.

Reference Point (type: real; extended; or integer): The reference year (or millennium, or latitude, or spatial transect coordinate, etc.) of the sampling window. It is expected that the Reference Point identifies a point (usually the midpoint) in the sampling window, though it is not necessary.

Specimens (sigma) (σ in Fig. 2 in Šizling et al., 202X; type: integer): The number of sampled specimens (e.g., individuals, artefacts, fossils, or pollen grains) collected in the sampling window. This information is not utilized by utility ETA 01, as this utility gains the σ (n of sampled specimens) by summing 'Specimens partial' from file 'In_03 [free text].txt'. If there is no information on the number of sampled specimens, the researcher is advised to use any integer larger than zero.

Span (type: real, extended or integer): The span of the sampling window in the same units as Reference Point (e.g., years, millennia, latitudinal extent, or meters in the case of a spatial transect, etc.). See Fig. 2 in Šizling et al. (202X) for the definition. For palaeontological data,

the researcher is free to use rounded values (e.g., 10 Myr). Span can also be termed ‘duration of the time or spatial bin.’ Span is a proxy for accumulation rate if sediments are sampled using the same sedimentation extent (e.g., one cm vertically).

File In_02 [free text].txt; List of Taxa; optional,

(only if one wishes to restrict the analysis to a subset of taxa (items, types of artefacts, etc.) in data to process)

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

List of Taxa (In_02) – **Velké ohbí** - Observed

Taxon Code Taxon

1 e.g., Empetrum-type, (or bronze axhead)

2 e.g., Quercus, or (bronze spearhead)

3 e.g., Ranunculus acris-type, (or amber jewellery)

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

The first line is free text, which is mandatory; otherwise, the first data line will not be processed. ‘Velké ohbí’ is the name of the site analysed.

Taxon Code (type: integer): A unique code for each taxon (item, type of artefact, etc.). This code identifies the unit whose appearance and disappearance from the assemblage is analysed.

Taxon (type: string): This free text stores information on particular taxa in biology, types of artefacts in archaeology, or any other items whose assemblages are analysed. The software does not utilize this information, so even an empty string (i.e., ‘ ’) or placeholder strings (e.g., ‘Nick-Nack’) are allowed. However, avoid using a tab character (code: #9).

Guide to the Episodic Trend Analysis (ETA) - version v0.1.0

File In_03 [free text].txt; required,

(records of taxa for each sample)

//////////////////////////////////Example Begin//////////////////////////////////

Records (In_03) – **Velké ohbí** – Observed

Sequence Code	Sample Code	Taxon Code	Specimens Partial
---------------	-------------	------------	-------------------

10	1	2	24
----	---	---	----

10	1	5	1
----	---	---	---

10	1	7	4
----	---	---	---

...

//////////////////////////////////Example End//////////////////////////////////

The first line is free text, which is mandatory; otherwise, the first data line will not be processed. 'Velké ohbí' is the name of the site analysed.

Sequence Code (type: integer): An identifier for the data series from your database (the same as in file 'In_01').

Sample Code (type: integer): An identifier for the sampling window (the same as in file 'In_01').

Taxon Code (type: integer): An identifier for a taxon (the same as in file 'In_02').

Specimens (partial) (type: integer): The number of sampled specimens (e.g., pollen grains, fragments of fossilized organisms, fragments of industry) corresponding to the respective 'Taxon Code' and 'Sample Code'. For example, if you have 30 fragments of snail shells, representing about 10 individuals, then 'Specimens (partial) = 30'. The total number of 'Specimens (partial)' across all Taxa (Taxon Codes) found within a sampling window (Sample Code) sums up to 'Specimens (sigma)' in file 'In_01'.

The Files on the Output

File Out_00 [free text].txt; optional

Sequence Code: See file 'In_01 [free text].txt'.

Reference Point: See file 'In_01 [free text].txt'.

Maximum Period: This refers to the period between the first and last sampling windows of a triplet of consecutive sampling windows.

Guide to the Episodic Trend Analysis (ETA) - version v0.1.0

Slope: This refers to the slope of the regression line between taxon richness and the periods between sampling windows.

Significance of Intercept (<0.01): This refers to the statistical significance of the intercept of the regression line.

Significance of Slope (<0.01): This refers to the statistical significance of the slope.

File Out_01 [free text].txt; required.

Headlines: There are three headlines in the file:

First, the free text adopted from file 'In_01 [free text].txt';

Second, details on setting (e.g., 2 [tabelator] 2 [tabelator] 3 [tabelator] samples to analyze in a row [tabelator] Logarithmic transformation). The first number is a code of transformation, the second number refers to 'Use the 2nd window' setting, and the third number refers to 'Use 3 sampling windows' setting.

Third, captions of the columns:

Sequence Code: See file 'In_01 [free text].txt'.

Reference Point: This refers to the Reference point of the selected sampling window from the consecutive sampling windows within the episode (usually the triplet); see file 'In_01 [free text].txt'. There are more (typically three) lines with the same Reference Point in the file. Each line captures information on one particular combination of two sampling windows within the episode.

T (transformed): Jaccard index (J) transformed as chosen in the 'Type of Transformation' setting (Eq. 1 in Šizling et al., 202X).

N (transformed): Simpson similarity (β'_{Sim}) transformed as chosen in the 'Type of Transformation' setting (Eq. 2 in Šizling et al., 202X).

G (transformed): Index of Taxon Richness Contrast ($\frac{S_{later}}{S_{earlier}}$) transformed as chosen in the 'Type of Transformation' setting (Eq. 3 in Šizling et al., 202X).

Period (p): Period between the two sampling windows.

Delta Sigma, or Delta Sigma per Taxon: Absolute value of the difference between the numbers of sampled specimens (σ) in the two sampling windows. If 'Use normalized N of Sampled Spec' is checked, the column refers to the absolute difference between σ/S (Sigma per Taxon), where S is the taxon richness.

Mean Sigma Reciprocal, or Mean Sigma per Taxon Reciprocal: Refers to $\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{w1}^{-1} + \sigma_{w2}^{-1})$, or $\frac{S}{2}(\sigma_{w1}^{-1} + \sigma_{w2}^{-1})$, respectively. The indexes $w1$ and $w2$ refer to the first and second sampling windows, and S stands for *Taxon Richness*.

Delta Span: Absolute value of the difference between the *Spans* of the two sampling windows.

Mean Span: Mean value of the *Spans* across the two sampling windows.

Mean Taxon Richness: Mean value of the *Taxon Richness* across the two sampling windows.

Setting

Type of Transformation: The checked logarithmic transformation indicates that the indices T, N are computed as in Eqs. 1,2 in Šizling et al. (202X). The index G always follows Eq. 3 in Šizling et al. (202X).

The checkboxes indicate alternative options for Eqs. 1,2, that are as follows:

$$T \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E(J) \quad \text{Eq. M1}$$

$$N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E(\beta'_{Sim}). \quad \text{Eq. M2}$$

The symbol 'E' stands for the transformation that is the subject of the following options:

No transformation: if checked, then $T \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} J, N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \beta'_{Sim}$.

logarithmic: see Eqs. 1,2 in Šizling et al. (202X).

logistic: if checked, then $T \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{logit}(J), N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{logit}(\beta'_{Sim})$.

LogLog: if is checked, then $T \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -\log(-\log(J)), N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -\log(-\log(\beta'_{Sim}))$.

For technical purposes, the logarithm is computed as $\log(I) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \ln \frac{I+null}{1+null}$, where $null = 10^{-4930}$. This approach provides a sufficiently accurate value for the logarithm and prevents the computation from collapsing when index I is too small.

Use 3 sampling windows: This option indicates that the computation is run for triples of consecutive sampling windows. While it is possible to use more than three sampling windows in a row, it is not recommended. Firstly, using more than three sampling windows extends the episodes within which we wish to detect a trend. Secondly, it decreases fluctuations in $r_{T,p}^*$ (see Šizling et al., 202X for the definition), which in turn reduces the number of episodes where the absence of a trend can be confirmed with certainty, and which are used to compute the range of randomness.

Use the 2nd window: This option indicates that each episode is identified by the reference point (e.g., year) of the second window. In the case of three sampling windows, the triplet is assigned to the sampling window in the middle.

Use linearized T and R: Unpublished method in development. Enabled in version v0.1.0

Use normalized N of Sampled Spec: If checked, the σ used to control for variation in sampling effort (see Utility ETA 02) is defined as the number of sampled specimens (e.g., pollen grains, artifacts) divided by taxon richness. If unchecked, σ is the raw number of sampled specimens.

Log Transformed Period btw Windows: If checked, the period between sampling window is logarithmically transformed. See **Type of Transformation** for technical definition of logarithm used in the analysis.

Utility ETA 02: Global Trend

This utility transforms the sampling effort so that the sampling effort parameters follow as normal frequency distribution as possible. The utility then fits a multivariate linear model to obtain parameters of global trends. These parameters are used to adjust the indices in order to eliminate the effect of variation in sampling effort. The fitting uses a random procedure to estimate parameters, so two runs with the same data may result in slightly different values. However, the detected trends should not differ between the two runs.

The Panel

 The screenshot shows a software window titled 'Utility_02'. It contains several sections:

- Buttons at the top: 'Load File for Prefitting (Out_01)', 'Save Prefitted Rates (Out_02)', and 'Save Parameters of Transformation (Out_03)'.
- Variable selection: A list of variables with checkboxes: '1 Site', '4 Trend', '5 Nestedness', '6 Gradient', '8 Period btw windows', '9 Diff in N of Specimens', '10 Reciprocal Mean of Specimens', '11 Diff in Span of windows', and '12 Mean Span of windows'. Below this is an 'Index:' field.
- Regression options: 'All Sites Regression' (unchecked), 'Mutual Constraints T,N,G' (unchecked), 'Iterate 0 times for regression', 'Include N of Sampled Specimens' (checked), 'Include Spans of Sampling Windows' (checked), 'Include Period between Windows' (checked), and 'without Data Transformation' (unchecked).
- Intercept: A checkbox for 'Intercept' which is checked, with a range '0 <=Intercept<= 1'.
- Sort by: A vertical list of '1' values next to the variable numbers, with an 'END' button to the right.
- Buttons at the bottom: 'RUN', 'Load List of Windows to Select (In_04)', and 'Load known Parameters of Transformation (Out_03)'.

Run the utility (basic): (i) load Out_01; (ii) save Out_02; (iii) save Out_03; (iv) load In_04, optional; (v) press RUN.

Run the utility (alternative): (i) load Out_01; (ii) save Out_02; (iii) load Out_03; (iv) load In_04, optional; (v) press RUN.

The Files on the Input

File '**Out_01 [free text].txt**': required;
(see the outputs from the Utility ETA 01)

File **In_04 [free text].txt**

(a list of trend-free sampling windows; this file is optional and should be used only if the researcher knows for certain that some sampling windows fall within an interval without a trend and if the list is statistically representative to all trend-free sampling windows, i.e., if the range of randomness in T^* of the list is the same as the range of randomness of all trend-free sampling windows)

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

Records (In_04) – Velké ohbí – Observed

2 3 3 samples to analyze in a row Logarithmic transformation

Sequence Code Reference Point

1 15142

1 14958

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

The first line is free text, which is mandatory; otherwise, the first data line will not be processed. 'Velké ohbí' is the name of the site analysed.

The second line is information on the setting. The first number and last sentence refers to the E transformation, the second number and following sentence refer to 'Use N sampling Windows' setting in Utility ETA 01. The researcher is advised to adopt the second line from file 'Out_01 [free text].txt'.

Sequence Code: the same as in In_01 [free text].txt'.

Reference Point: the same as in In_01 [free text].txt'.

The Files on the Output

Files '**Out_02 [free text].txt**' and '**Out_03 [free text].txt**': These are internal files to transfer information between Utilities ETA 02 and ETA 03. File Out_02 preserves parameters of the multivariable linear model (Eqs. M3-M5), and file Out_03 preserves parameters of the T , N , G transformations (Eq. M6).

The Options

Loading In_04 (optional): This restricts the analysis to the loaded list of sampling windows. It may improve the pre-fitted rates of diversity if we know that some sites are trend-free for certain. The reason is that the pre-fitted rates are supposed to capture the retrogression (entire trend of the whole sequence of assemblages) and therefore should preferentially be controlled out of the short-time trends. **We recommend that the user employ this option only if they are absolutely certain of the representative list of trend-free sampling windows;** otherwise, a bias may be introduced into the analysis.

Load Out_03 (alternative): This option is used if the parameters of transformations are already known. The format of the file 'Out_03' to load, and the format of the file Out_03 to save ('Save ... Out_03' button) are identical.

Details on the Algorithm

The values of T,N,G are affected by the sampling effort. If the sampling effort is low, rare species are missing from the data, resulting in biased indices. We utilize two three main parameters of sampling effort: (i) the period between sampling windows (p); (ii) the time span of the sampling window (τ), and (iii) the number of specimens in the sample (σ , Fig. 1 in Šizling et al., 202X).

The tool introduced here employs a generalized multivariable linear models for the relationships between the indices and parameters of sampling effort:

$$T = r_{T,p}F_p(p) + r_{T,\tau}F_\tau(\tau) + r_{T,\Delta\tau}F_{\Delta\tau}(\Delta\tau) + r_{T,\sigma}F_\sigma(\sigma^{-1}) + r_{T,\Delta\sigma}F_{\Delta\sigma}(\Delta\sigma) + T_0, \quad (\text{Eq. M3})$$

$$N = r_{N,p}F_p(p) + r_{N,\tau}F_\tau(\tau) + r_{N,\Delta\tau}F_{\Delta\tau}(\Delta\tau) + r_{N,\sigma}F_\sigma(\sigma^{-1}) + r_{N,\Delta\sigma}F_{\Delta\sigma}(\Delta\sigma) + N_0, \quad (\text{Eq. M4})$$

$$|G| = r_{G,p}F_p(p) + r_{G,\tau}F_\tau(\tau) + r_{G,\Delta\tau}F_{\Delta\tau}(\Delta\tau) + r_{G,\sigma}F_\sigma(\sigma^{-1}) + r_{G,\Delta\sigma}F_{\Delta\sigma}(\Delta\sigma) + G_0. \quad (\text{Eq. M5})$$

Here r stands for the rates, and p, τ, σ follow the terminology in Fig. 1. The delta operators $\Delta\tau$ and $\Delta\sigma$ stand for the absolute values of the differences between τ and σ . We refer to $p, \tau, \sigma^{-1}, \Delta\tau, \Delta\sigma$ as sampling parameters. All sampling parameters were power-transformed using

$$F_x(x) = (x/c_{2x})^{c_{1x}}/c_{3x} \quad (\text{Eq. M6})$$

to obtain as symmetric distribution of $F_x(x)$ as possible. The F-transformed values have the mean value equal to one. In Eq. M6, the x is to be replaced with sampling parameters - e.g., $F_\tau(\tau) = (\tau/c_{2\tau})^{c_{1\tau}}/c_{3\tau}$. The parameter values of c_{1x}, \dots, c_{3x} , are determined by a random process.

Utility ETA 02 fits Eqs. M3-M5 to data on the entire data-series to extract the rates, r . The rates $r_{I,\tau}, r_{I,\Delta\tau}, r_{I,\sigma}, r_{I,\Delta\sigma}$ capture the scaling between the index I and the sampling parameters (where symbol I stands for T, N, G). The rates $r_{I,p}$ represent the rates of the overall retrogressive trends. We then use all these rates to estimate what the observed values of T, N, G would have been if

there were no variations in the sampling parameters. This is achieved by computing the residuals between the model and the observations, and summing these residuals with the indices computed by equations M3-M5 into which we plug the pre-selected sampling parameters. See Šizling et al. (202X) for further details.

Setting

All Sites Regression: If checked, and if multiple sequences are processed at once, then the regression utilizes data from all sequences in files 'In_01', 'In_02', 'In_03'. Otherwise, each sequence is fitted separately. This option should be used when processing ecologically and geographically similar data, where identical relationships between sampling parameters and indices are expected.

Iterate 0 times for regression: If 0 is entered, then the equations are fitted using Least Square Regression and the Gauss elimination method, optimizing the residuals between observed and modeled values of T,N,G. If a number greater than 0 is entered (e.g., 10^3), then the algorithm minimizes the squares of residuals between the model and observation for $\text{Transf}(T)$, $\text{Transf}(N)$ and $\text{Transf}(G)$. The operator 'Transf' stands for the inverse transformation to the transformation 'E()' chosen in Utility ETA_01 (the options: Type of Transformation), and a randomization procedure is employed. For Eqs. 1-3 in Šizling et al. (202X), $\text{Transf}(I) \equiv \text{Exp}(I)$ where I stands for T, N, and G.

Include N of Sampled Specimens: If unchecked, then $r_{I,\sigma} = 0$, and $r_{I,\Delta\sigma} = 0$ as default values (I stands for T,N, or G).

Include Spans of Sampling Windows: If unchecked, then $r_{I,\tau} = 0$, and $r_{I,\Delta\tau} = 0$ as default values (I stands for T,N, or G).

Include Period between Windows: If unchecked, then $r_{I,p} = 0$ as a default value (I stands for T,N, or G).

Without data Transformation: if checked, then $c_{1x} = 1$, $c_{2x} = 1$ and $c_{3x} = 1$ for all x, as default values.

Intercept: If checked, the intercepts of equations Eq. M3, and Eq. M4 fall between E – transformed minimum and maximum intercept limits set in the panel above this checkbox. That is, $E(\text{Min } I) \leq T_0 \leq E(\text{Max } I)$ and $E(\text{Min } I) \leq N_0 \leq E(\text{Max } I)$, where Min I and Max I are values from the intercept banners, and E is the transformation from Eqs. M1, and M2.

The options **Variable** and **Sort by** are internal settings that refer to the rank of the variables in the files. Modification is not recommended.

Utility ETA 03: Sampling Effort

This utility converts T, N, G into T^*, N^*, G^* using the parameters calculated by Utility ETA 02. It also calculate slope of regression line between index T and period (p), $r_{T,p}^*$.

The Panel

Controlled analysis: (i) set the reference point in panel 'Setting': fill p^* into reference period between sampling windows'; fill τ^* into reference span of sampling windows; fill σ^* into reference number of sampled specimens (see section 'The values to standardize sampling effort ($p^*, \tau^*, \sigma^*, \Delta\tau^*, \Delta\sigma^*$)' in Šizling et al., 202X). The default value of $\Delta\tau^*$, and $\Delta\sigma^*$ is zero; (ii) load files 'In_01', 'Out_01', 'Out_02', 'Out_03'; (iii) check 'Trend', 'Nestedness' and 'Gradient' checkboxes in panel 'Setting II'; (iv) set other options on panels 'Setting' and 'setting II'; (v) create file 'Out_04 [free text] Control.txt', required; (vi) create file 'Out_05 [free text] Control.txt', optional; (vii) press RUN; (viii) do not terminate the Utility.

Uncontrolled analysis: (i) uncheck 'Trend', 'Nestedness' and 'Gradient' checkboxes in panel 'Setting II'; (ii) keep all other options on panels 'Setting' and 'Setting II'; (iii) create file 'Out_04 [free text] UnControl.txt', required; (iv) create file 'Out_05 [free text] UnControl.txt', optional; (v) press RUN.

Combined analysis: This analysis is the issue of Utility ETA 07.

The Files on the Input

File '**In_01 [free text].txt**': see instructions for Utility ETA 01

File '**Out_01 [free text].txt**': see instructions for Utility ETA 01

File '**Out_02 [free text].txt**': see instructions for Utility ETA 02

File '**Out_03 [free text].txt**': see instructions for Utility ETA 02

The Files on the Output

Files '**Out_04 [free text] Control.txt**' and '**Out_04 [free text] UnControl.txt**' are internal files to transfer information between Utilities ETA 03 and ETA 04. Most of the variables in these files are E-transformed or F-transformed (Eqs. M1, M2, M6).

File '**Out_05 [free text].txt**': Enabled in version v0.1.0.

Setting

Significance level: significance level for rates of change in T,N,G with increasing p , σ , $\Delta\sigma$, τ and $\Delta\tau$. It does not refer to the power of the trend detection. The power of detection is assessed by analysing simulated assemblages with data-specific sampling effort. The significance level is not utilized if the checkbox 'involve significance ...' is unchecked.

Involve significance of the pre-fitted values: If checked, then all insignificant rates $r_{I,x}$ in Eqs. M3-M5 are automatically set equal to zero (I stands for index and x stands for variable).

N of steps when fitting: Enabled in version v0.1.0.

Figures Options: Enabled in version v0.1.0.

Take info on the sum from details: If checked, It utilizes information on σ and $\Delta\sigma$ to eliminate variation in sampling effort from file 'In_01 [free text].txt, column' 'Specimens (sigma)'. Otherwise it utilizes this information from file 'In_03 [free text].txt', column 'Specimens Partial'.

Ref period between windows: p^* , see section 'The values to standardize sampling effort ($p^*, \tau^*, \sigma^*, \Delta\tau^*, \Delta\sigma^*$)' in Šizling et al., (202X).

Ref Span of windows: τ^* , see section 'The values to standardize sampling effort ($p^*, \tau^*, \sigma^*, \Delta\tau^*, \Delta\sigma^*$)' in Šizling et al. (202X).

Ref N of Sampled Specimens: σ^* , see section 'The values to standardize sampling effort ($p^*, \tau^*, \sigma^*, \Delta\tau^*, \Delta\sigma^*$)' in Šizling et al. (202X).

Method for T-distribution: This method calculates the 95% or 99% quantiles of T^* , N^* , and G^* . If the 'Table Values' option is checked, the Utility ETA 02 uses tabled quantiles of the Student distribution. Otherwise, the quantiles are computed numerically with N fitting steps. However, the numerical method is slower and less accurate, so it is generally not recommended.

Control for variation in sampling effort: If Trend is checked, then the Eq. 3 is utilized; if Nestedness is checked, then the Eq. 4 is utilized; If Gradient is checked, then the Eq. 5 is utilized.

Control for Slopes: A method in development; enabled in version v0.1.0.

Adjust Mean Values and Trend-Nestedness-Gradient regression: Unpublished method in development. Enabled in version v0.1.0.

Increase in SR is taken from mean values: If checked, then increase in Taxon-Richness is detected with increasing regression line between Taxon-Richness and time across each triple of sampling windows. Otherwise it is detected with signum of index G. Although 'checked' approach seems more straightforward (if SR visually increases, then it must increase), it is less accurate to determine inequality $\pi_{App} > \pi_{Dis}$, and we do not recommend it.

Utility ETA 04: Detecting Episodic Trends

This utility calculates ranges of randomness and detects episodic trends. It generates data for Diagnostic Plots and shows them in file 'Out_06 [free text].txt'

The Panel

Run the utility (basic): (i) load Out_4 [free text] Control; (ii) modify setting (optional); (iii) create Out_06 [free text] Control; (iv) press RUN; (v) load Out_04 [free text] UnControl; (vi) create Out_06 [free text] UnControl; (vii) press RUN;

The Files on the Input

File **Out_04 [free text].txt (mandatory):** This is the output from Utility ETA 03.

File **Out_00 [free text].txt (optional):** This is the output from Utility ETA 01. It is only relevant if the 'Richness-Time Relationship' option is checked in the 'Method to Identify Trend in Taxon Richness' panel.

The File on the Output

File **Out_06 [free text].txt**

(the final output without calibration)

Sequence Code: See file In_01 [free text].txt.

Reference Point: See file Out_01 [free text].txt.

Significance level for T^* : This is the probability that the value of T^* for a trend-free triplet of consecutive sampling windows (i.e., an episode to test for a trend where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$) is accidentally smaller than the bottom limit of the range of randomness for T^* . This value is filled in the 'Significance level for T^* ' banner. It is recommended to fill the 'Significance level for T^* ' banner with '0'. In this case, the significance level is calculated using the formula Eq. M7 in the 'Practical Notes' section below. It is recommended that the researcher uses the same significance level for T^* , N^* , and G^* . Therefore only significance level for T^* is listed in the output file in version v0.1.0.

Quantile Threshold for T^* : The bottom limit of the range of randomness for T^* . It is shown in the Diagnostic Plot T^* as a dashed horizontal line.

Quantile Threshold for N^* : The bottom limit of the range of randomness for N^* . It is shown in the Diagnostic Plot for N^* as a dashed horizontal line.

Quantile Threshold for G^* : The half extent of the range of randomness for G^* . The bottom and upper limits of the range of randomness for G^* equal mean G^* across the trend-free episodes (i.e., where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$) minus/plus the listed number. The bottom and upper limits are shown as dashed horizontal lines in the Diagnostic Plot for G^* .

SD of T^* without a Trend: Standard deviation of T^* across trend-free episodes (i.e., where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$).

SD of N^* without a Trend: Standard deviation of N^* across trend-free episodes (i.e., where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$).

SD of G^* without a Trend: Standard deviation of G^* across trend-free episodes (i.e., where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$).

'Rate of T(p) (detected)' or 'T* (detected)': If T^* is utilized in the Diagnostic Plot (the option 'Employ Mean Values of T' is checked), then this column shows $r_{T,p}^*$. If 'Employ Mean Values of T' is unchecked, this column shows detected values of T^* . The first option is recommended, as otherwise the trend-free episodes used to calculate the range of randomness are unlikely to be representative.

'T* (detected)' or 'Rate of T(p) (detected)': If $r_{T,p}^*$ is shown in the previous column, the detected values of T^* are shown in this column, and vice versa.

'N* (detected)' or 'Rate of N(p) (detected)': If N^* is utilized in the Diagnostic Plot (the option 'Employ Mean Values of N' is checked), then this column shows detected values of N^* . If 'Employ Mean Values of N' is unchecked, this column shows $r_{N,p}^*$ (i.e., the slope of the regression line of $N(p)$ across the triplet of consecutive sampling windows within the tested episode; $N(p)$ is adjusted for variation in sampling effort; see Šizling et al., 202X for details). The first option is recommended; else the trend-free episodes that are employed to calculate the range of randomness are unlikely representative.

Proxy for Trend Intensity (detected): $\ln((|T^*| + |N^*| + Null)/(1 + Null))$ where $Null = 10^{-7}$.

'G* (detected)' or 'Rate of G(p) (detected)': If G^* is utilized in the Diagnostic Plot (the option 'Employ Mean Values of G' is checked), then this column shows detected values of G^* . If 'Employ Mean Values of G' is unchecked, this column shows $r_{G,p}^*$ (slope of regression line of $G(p)$ across the triplet of consecutive sampling windows within the tested episode; $G(p)$ is adjusted for variation in sampling effort; see Šizling et al., 202X for details). The first option is recommended; as otherwise the trend-free episodes used to calculate the range of randomness are unlikely to be representative.

Taxon Richness (detected): Detected Taxon Richness.

Significance of T*: The probability that the T^* of a trend-free episode is smaller than the detected T^* . Utility ETA 04 indicates trends by comparing this significance with the '**Significance level for T***'. This comparison is equivalent to comparing the detected T^* with the bottom limit of the range of randomness for T^* . Numerical issues may cause slight differences between these two approaches, although it is unlikely.

Significance of N*: The probability that the N^* of a trend-free episode is smaller than the detected N^* . Utility ETA 04 indicates the trends with significant Nestedness (T1,T2) by comparing this significance with the '**Significance level for N***' (which should be identical to '**significance level for T***'). This comparison is equivalent to comparing detected N^* with the bottom limit of the range of randomness for N^* . Numerical issues may cause slight differences between these two comparisons, although it is unlikely.

Significance of G*: The probability that the G^* of a trend-free episode is smaller or larger than the detected G^* (see Diagnostic Plot of G^*). Utility ETA 04 indicates trends with significant Taxon-Richness Gradient (T1,T2,T4,T5) by comparing this significance with the '**Significance level for G***' (which should be identical to the '**significance level for T***'). This comparison is equivalent to comparing the detected G^* with the bottom and upper limits of the range of randomness for G^* . Numerical issues may cause slight differences between these two comparisons, although it is unlikely.

Trend Type (detected): Detected trend type (T0-T5), where 'T0' indicates the episodes with no trend detected.

Setting

Significance Levels for T^* , N^* , G^* : The number filled in the banner indicates the quantile of the range of randomness. For instance, if 0.05 is the number filled, then only 5% of trend-free episodes can be found out of the range of randomness by chance. If set to zero, Utility_04 uses Eq. M7 (see 'Practical Notes') to calculate the significance level, which is uniquely determined for each data sequence. The zero option is recommended.

Index Banner: It informs the researcher about the analysis progress. It is useful when processing multiple sequences. On some computers, this may stop displaying due to Windows functions, even though the analysis continues running.

Known SD of Randomness for T^* , N^* , and G^* : If checked, Utility ETA 04 uses the provided values of standard deviation (SD) and degrees of freedom (Df), instead of calculating ranges of randomness from the trend-free episodes where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$. Use this option only if SD values are known from data with similar ecology and taphonomy.

Employ Mean Values of T , N , and G : If checked, the trends are detected from T^* , N^* , and G^* values, as described in Šizling et al., (202X). Otherwise, trends are detected from $r_{T,p}^*$, $r_{N,p}^*$, and $r_{G,p}^*$. Using mean values is recommended.

Negative rates [...] positive rates of T : Method in development; enabled in version v0.1.0.

Existence of Trend from T^*+N^* , T^*+G^* , and N^* : When none of these options is checked, only the bottom limit of T^* randomness range is used for trend detection (i.e., there is a trend if the significance of T^* is smaller than its significance level) as described in Šizling et al. (202X). Additional criteria can be added as follows:

T^*+N^* : Utility ETA 04 detects trends where the average significance of T^* and N^* is smaller than their average significance level.

T^*+G^* : Utility ETA 04 detects trends where the average significance of T^* and G^* is smaller than their average significance level.

N^* : Utility ETA 04 detects trends where the significance of N^* is smaller than its significance level.

Guide to the Episodic Trend Analysis (ETA) - version v0.1.0

The left-side figure shows the Diagnostic Plot for Velké ohbí data with the 'Existence of Trend from' options unchecked. The right-side figure shows the Diagnostic Plot for the same analysis, with the only difference being that the 'T*+N*' option is checked. In the first case, the trend is determined using only T* values, so all the episodes with detected trends (red squares) have their T* values below the bottom limit of the range of randomness (gray dashed horizontal line). In the second case, there is an episode with T* above the bottom limit of the range of randomness for T* (red square above the gray dashed horizontal line). This occurs because this episode has an insignificant T* but a significant T* and N* together. Nevertheless, the dashed horizontal line shows an important limit in both cases. Large blue balls represent the episodes that are certainly trend-free (those with $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$), while small black rings indicate the episodes where the absence of a trend was detected.

Method for T-Values: Utility ETA 04 calculates significances and ranges for T^* , N^* , and G^* . If both 'Table Values' and 'Student Distribution' are checked, tabled quantiles of the Student distribution are used. If both 'Numerical Approach' and 'Student Distribution' are checked, the quantiles are calculated numerically with N fitting steps (slower and less accurate option). If 'Laplace Distribution' is checked, the Laplace distribution is used, and its quantiles are calculated analytically (i.e., from equations for the Laplace distribution) regardless of this setting.

Method to Identify the Trends: Enabled in version v0.1.0.

Method to Identify Windows without Nestedness: Enabled in version v0.1.0.

Method to Identify Trend in Taxon Richness:

G^* : Utility ETA 04 follows the procedure from Šizling et al. (202X). Positive G^* identifies an increase in Taxon-Richness, while negative G^* identifies a decrease in Taxon-Richness.

Richness-Time Relationship: Utility ETA 04 identifies increases in taxon richness from positive slopes of regression lines for $G(p)$ values plotted against their corresponding p values across each triplet of consecutive sampling windows. Decreases in taxon richness are identified from negative slopes. G is adjusted for variation in sampling effort (Šizling et al., 202X). This option requires file 'Out_00 [free text].txt'. Although this option seems to be more straightforward, the ' G^* ' option provides better results.

Sequences Management:

Separate Sequence Calculation: Utility ETA 04 analyses each data sequence with a unique 'Sequence Code' separately.

All Sequences Calculation: Utility ETA 04 analyses all data sequences together using the same range of randomness. This option is recommended for sequences with similar ecology and taphonomy.

Student vs Laplace Distribution for T^* , N^* and G^* :

Student Distribution: Utility ETA 04 calculates ranges of randomness as confidence intervals of the Student Distribution (bottom-sided confidence intervals for T^* , and N^* , and two-sided confidence interval for G^*).

Laplace Distribution: Utility ETA 04 uses confidence intervals of the Laplace distribution for ranges of randomness. Both the Student and Laplace distribution options yield similar results. If the researcher wishes to determine which distribution is better, they can plot histograms for T^* , N^* , and G^* from episodes where $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$ taken from file 'Out_06 [free text].txt'.

Use 3 SD criterion: Utility ETA 04 uses 3SD criterion (also referred to as 3σ criterion) when calculating the ranges of randomness. This option is recommended only if the histograms of T^* , N^* , or G^* for episodes with $r_{T,p}^* \geq 0$ show outliers.

Adjust: Method in development; enabled in version v0.1.0.

Diagnostic Plot: Press this button before pressing the 'RUN' button to generate the diagnostic plots. Diagnostic plots can also be created manually using data from file 'Out_06 [free text].txt'. When processing simulated sequences, using this option will slow down the analysis and is therefore not recommended.

Utility ETA 07: Combined Analysis

This utility combines Controlled and Uncontrolled analyses together into file 'Out_06 [free text] Combined.txt'

The Panel

Run the utility: (i) load Out_06 [free text] Control, and Out_06 [free text] UnControl; (ii) create Out_06 [free text] Combined; (iii) press RUN.

The Files on the Input

File **Out_06 [free text] Control.txt**: This file is an output from Utility ETA 04.

File **Out_06 [free text] UnCombined.txt**: This file is an output from Utility ETA 04.

The File on Output

File **Out_06 [free text] Combined.txt**: This file is the final output from the analysis without a calibration. For the caption of the headlines see Utility ETA 04 above.

Part 2

Calibration of the Analysis

Main Idea

The primary method of calibration relies on an assemblage-by-assemblage simulation of several artificial sequences with known and varying types of trends and their intensities (I_T , I_G). Each assemblage lasts for a duration of one year, century, millennium, etc., depending on the time units used in the data series (Year, Myr, etc.). The same can be expressed in terms of spatial transect or any other Reference Axis.

Each artificial sequence includes randomly distributed episodes with and without trends. These episodes last for three or more sampling windows, because the method is not designed to detect shorter trends. These artificial sequences are then sampled as real data and processed using the same analysis method (see Part 1 above). The match between known (input to the simulation) and detected trends demonstrates the accuracy of the analysis, assuming the variation in sampling effort is consistent between the observed and artificial data.

The relationships between the estimated, uncalibrated rates and known intensities (I_T , and I_G) are used to calibrate the rates extracted from the data. For method verification, we ran two sets of simulations: one for calibration and one to validate the calibration process. This validation showed that the calibration works. However, for data calibration, this step is not necessary. Therefore, we recommend that users run the calibration only once.

Utility ETA 101: Generator of Artificial Data

This utility generates artificial data on assemblages to calibrate the analysis and test the efficiency of the method.

The Panel

Run the Utility (basic):

Generate Development of Assemblage (app 90 min with 'In_101 [free text] FAST.txt' driving file).

- (i) Modify the 'Ref Point Min' and 'Ref Point Max' in the driver of the simulation, file 'In_101 [free text].txt' (the attached universal file 'In_101 Driver FAST.txt' is recommended).
- (ii) Load the modified Driver of the Simulation 'In_101 [free text].txt'.
- (iii) Set min and max Taxon Richness according to the data analysed (researchers should set a range broader than the observed extremes). If the simulated assemblage exceeds the set range, the trend type will switch between trend types T1 <-> T2, or T4 <-> T5 to keep taxon richness within realistic limits

- (iv) Load data-specific files In_102 and In_104; these files contain sampling data and are needed to plan the episodes with a trend, minimizing the chance of simulating episodes shorter than N sampling windows (N=3 by default; see Settings).
- (v) Press 'Save Sequences' button to create file Out_110.
- (vi) Press the 'Run the Sequences' button.

Run a Taphonomic Selection

(this part of the simulation is irrelevant for many datasets, e.g., spatial transect data; see 'Details on the Depth – Age Model' section below)

- (vii) Press the 'Save File for Sampled Sequences' button to create file 'Out_111 [free text].txt';
- (viii) Press the 'RUN the Sequence Sampling' button to perform the first part of the sampling (taphonomic). *This process combines taphonomic selection with researcher-imposed sampling, hence, we refer to the entire process as sampling.*

Run the Final Part of the Sampling and Convert 'In_111' File into 'In_01'-'In_03' Data Formats:

- (ix) Press the 'Save Inputs to the ETA Utilities' button to create files 'In_01 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt', 'In_02 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt' and 'In_03 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt' to be analysed like field data (see Part 1 of this Manual).
- (x) Load data-specific files In_103 (optional, see section 'Setting') and 'In_105[free text].txt', or 'In_03 [free text].txt'.
- (xi) Check or uncheck the 'Involve Sampling Effect' option (see section 'Setting').
- (xii) Press the 'Convert' button to convert the sampled sequences ('Out_111 [free text].txt') into files 'In_01 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt', 'In_02 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt', and 'In_03 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt' for analysis like real-world data (see Part 1 of this Guide).

An alternative Utility Run 1

- (i) Follow the points (i), (ii), (iii), (iv), (vi),(v), (ix) (x) and (xi) from the basic run schedule above.
- (ii) Press the 'All in One Run' button.

An alternative Utility Run 2

(Useful if the assemblage has already been generated and the researcher needs to use another sampling with different effort)

- (i) Press the 'Load Sequences of Assemblages' button to load file 'Out_110 [free text].txt'.
- (ii) Follow the points from (vii) onwards in the basic run schedule above.

An alternative Utility Run 3

(Useful if the sampled assemblages are available but there is a need for conversion into files suitable for analysis)

- (i) Press the 'Load Sampled Sequences' button to load file 'Out_111 [free text].txt'.
- (ii) Follow the points from (ix) onwards in the basic run schedule above.

Details on the Depth – Age Model

The plot (A) shows the Depth - Age model, which represents a sedimentation process, assigning each centimeter of sediment to different years BP due to varying sedimentation rates. For transect data (B), this model is replaced with a Length-Length model, where both columns contain identical values. For archaeological or palaeontological data (C), where the age of each layer is known, it is replaced with an Age-Age model. These identity models (B, C) are necessary because this sampling step cannot be omitted for versatility. In each case, the second column represents the Reference Axis, with Reference Points in years BP for (A), kilometers for (B), and million years BP for (C).

The Files on the Input

File '**In_101 [free text].txt**'; a driver of the simulation.

This file is universal for all data analyses and is attached to the Utilities to run. The researcher can choose from different driving files: (i) Files with intensity of trend-less episodes (I_{T0}) relative to the trend intensity (I_T) of the episodes with a trend. These files are named with according to this proportion, e.g., '**In_101 [free text] 10%.txt**', meaning that $I_{T0} = 0.1I_T$; and (ii) a universal driving file with varying values of I_{T0} and I_T , e.g., '**In_101 [free text] FAST.txt**'. The 'FAST' driver is recommended for standard analyses.

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

In_101 Driving File - Universal (10-100%)

Sequence Code	Ref Point	Min	Ref Point	Max	Trend End	Trend Start	Intensity of T0	Trend Intensity	Gradient Intensity	Trend Type
1	0	10000	5736	7736	0.0005	0.003	0.006	1		
2	0	10000	6799	8799	0.0055	0.006	0.012	1		
3	0	10000	6199	8199	0.0032	0.009	0.018	1		

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

Sequence Code (type: integer): See file In_01 [free text].txt.

Ref Point Min (type: integer): Minimum Reference Point of the sequence to generate (e.g., year for timelines, kilometres for spatial transects).

Ref Point Max (type: integer): Maximum Reference Point of the sequence to generate.

Trend End (type: integer; the smaller number): All assemblages between 'Trend End' and 'Trend Start' are subject to the trend type specified in the 'Trend Type' column. This value is only applicable if the 'scattered event design' option is unchecked; see the 'Setting' section for details.

Trend Start (type: integer; the larger number): All assemblages between 'Trend End' and 'Trend Start' are subject to the trend type specified in the 'Trend Type' column if the 'scattered event design' option is unchecked, see the 'Setting' section for details.

Intensity of T0 (type: extended): Intensity of taxa turnover in trend-free periods (I_{T0}).

Trend Intensity (type: extended): Intensity of taxa turnover in periods with a trend (I_T).

Gradient Intensity (type: extended): Intensity of taxon richness gradient in periods with a trend (I_G).

Trend Type (type: integer): Type of trend (only one type of trend per simulated sequence); the trend type switches from T1 to T2, T4 to T5, T2 to T1, or T5 to T4 if taxon richness crosses the set limits; see section 'Setting'.

File **In_102 [free text].txt**, Depth-Age Relationship (Depth-Age Model).

This file is specific to timelines and data on fossil, sub(fossil) or artefact assemblages. For assemblages that were sampled directly, this file follows an identity model, meaning the same number is placed in both the 'Age' and 'Depth' columns (see 'Details on the Depth – Age Model' section above).

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

Depth-Age Model (In_102) – Sequence Name - Observed

Sequence Code Age Depth

10	684	8
10	847	10
10	1037	12
10	1227	14

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

Sequence Code: see file 'In_01 [free text].txt'.

Age (type: integer): This column contains values that correspond to the Reference Points in other files, ensuring consistency across different parts of the analysis. We labeled it 'Age' for conservative reasons, as this table is always referred to as the Depth-Age Model. Not all samples need to have an 'Age' value; sometimes, only specific samples have known ages, determined through methods such as C14 dating. In such cases, the 'Age' column will contain the known ages of those specific samples, while undated samples are not listed in the file. For spatial transect data and other gradients, the 'Age' column records the spatial coordinates of the samples. If the data follows another gradient, such as energy or temperature, the respective values (e.g., energy or temperature) are placed in this column. See the 'Details on the Depth-Age Model' section above.

Depth (type: integer): In the case of data extracted from sediments, it represents the depth of the dated sample. For data where a Depth–Age model does not apply (e.g., spatial transect data), the same number as in the 'Age' column must be filled. See the section 'Details on Depth – Age Model' above.

Guide to the Episodic Trend Analysis (ETA) - version v0.1.0

File **In_103 [free text].txt**; Optional; Sampled Specimens (σ).

(see the section 'Setting' for an alternative)

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

Sampled Specimens (In_103) – Site Name - Observed

Sequence Code Reference PointSpecimens Sampled

10 684 895

10 847 992

10 1037 1251

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

Sequence Code: See file 'In_01 [free text].txt'.

Reference Point: See file 'Out_01 [].txt'.

Specimens Sampled (type: integer): σ , the number of specimens (e.g., artefacts, pollen grains) in the sample. If file In_103 [free text].txt is loaded, the sampling follows the numbers of sampled specimens in the file. Thus, the number of sampled specimens varies between sampling windows in the same way as in the observed data-series.

File **In_104 [free text].txt**; Sampling Scheme

(this file combines information with the Depth – Age model to imitate equal sampling biases in artificial data and observation)

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

Sampling Scheme (In_104) - Site Name - Observed

Sequence Code Sample Code Min Depth Max Depth

10 1 7 8

10 2 17 18

10 3 27 28

10 4 30 32

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

Guide to the Episodic Trend Analysis (ETA) - version v0.1.0

Sequence Code(type: integer): An identifier of the sequence.

Sample Code(type: integer): An identifier of the sampling window.

Min Depth (type: integer): The upper limit of the sampling window below the surface if it is the real depth. As shown in Figures in the section '*Details on Depth – Age Model*', it is the minimum Reference Point of the sampling window in general.

Max Depth (type: integer): The lower limit of the sampling window.

File **In_105 [free text].txt**; Optional; Frequency Distribution of σ (i.e., specimen numbers, or abundances).

(optional, file 'In_03 [free text].txt' can be loaded instead; the tabulated σ are fitted with a log-normal distribution. The simulated σ values are then drawn randomly from this log-normal distribution)

////////////////////////////////////Example Begin////////////////////////////////////

Abundances (In_105) – Site Name - Observed

Sequence Code Sample Code Sampled Specimens

10 1 24

10 1 1

10 1 4

...

////////////////////////////////////Example End////////////////////////////////////

Sequence Code(type: integer): An identifier of the sequence.

Sample Code(type: integer): An identifier of sampling window.

Sampled Specimens (type: integer): The number of sampled specimens in the sampling window, σ .

The Files on the Output

File **Out_110 [free text].txt**: This file transfers information needed for calibration along the Reference Axis. This information includes the variation of diversity, taxon richness, underlying intensities, and trend types.

File **Out_111 [free text].txt**: This transfers information needed for calibration , specifically the sampled data from file 'Out_110 [free text].txt'.

The Info Banners

Reference Point Runs From 'X' to 'Y': Information on the extent of the Reference Point adopted from file 'In_101 [free text].txt'. Do not modify these banners manually.

Sequence/Assemblage: Information on the generated Sequence and Assemblage codes.

Setting

Scattered design: If checked, then the trend episodes do not follow the specification of one long, continuous trend interval from the driving file ('In_101'). Instead, several trend episodes covering three sampling windows are randomly scattered within the artificial sequence. When these episodes overlap, then the episodes of the generated trend last longer than three consecutive sampling windows. This setting is more realistic because the method focuses on shorter episodes driven or triggered by disturbances. However, the efficiency of the method decreases because the ability to detect a trend is always lower at the beginning and end of a trend episode, and because more trend episodes result in more starting and ending points.

Leave Sequences with less than 3 sampling windows: This option excludes sequences with extremely short trend episodes (less than 3 windows) from the test and calibration. It is necessary because the method is not designed to identify trends shorter than three sampling windows. While the method can detect shorter episodes, including them would bias the calibration. The sensitivity of the method to shorter trends is due to the fact that a very short trend episode falling between two sampling windows causes a non-random change in the assemblage. However, the method overestimates the length of such episodes.

Involve Sampling Effect via N Specimens: If checked, the sampling from assemblage takes place, which decreases the number of detected taxa in each assemblage.

Min and Max Numbers of Sampled Specimens: If file 'In_103 [free text].txt' is not loaded, then each assemblage is sampled with a number of specimens randomly drawn between these limits. If file 'In_103 [free text].txt' is loaded, then each assemblage is sampled with a number of specimens drawn from log-normal distribution fitted to the real values of the sampling tabled in this file.

Min and Max Taxon Richness: The range of taxon richness in the artificial data should follow the range of taxon richness in the real sequence of assemblages. We recommend setting Maximum Taxon Richness to three times higher than the observed maximum taxon richness to cover more scenarios than observed.

Utility ETA 05: Link Data and Simulation

The artificial sequences produced by Utility ETA 101 are processed in the same way as the observed data-sequences (Part 1 of this Guide). The result of this analysis is the file 'Out_06 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt'. This file needs to be linked to file 'Out_110 [free text].txt' or 'Out_111 [free text].txt' to compare the detected and known trends. Linking these files is the purpose of Utility ETA 05.

The Panel

Run the utility: (i) load file 'Out_06 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt'; (ii) load file 'Out_110 [free text].txt' or 'Out_111 [free text].txt'; (iii) create file 'Out_07 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt'; (iv) press the 'RUN' button; (v) Press the 'Summary Table' button and create file 'Out_08 [free text].txt'; (vi) press the 'END' button (it deletes all working files created during the utility run).

The Files On the Input

File **Out_06 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt**: This file is an output of Utilities ETA 06, or ETA 07 with simulated sequences as their inputs.

File **Out_110 [free text].txt**, or **Out_111 [free text].txt**: These files are outputs of Utility ETA 101.

The Files On the Output

File **Out_07 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt**: This file links together information about the underlying trend types and intensities with the results of the analysis. It consists of all columns from file 'Out_06 [free text] CALIBRATION.txt' plus the columns as follows:

Trend Code (known): Type of the trend (T0-T5) from the driver of the simulation (file 'In_101' as input to the generator).

Trend Intensity (known): I_T (or I_{T0}) from the driver of the simulation (file 'In_101' as input to the generator).

Gradient Intensity (known): I_G from the driver of the simulation (file 'In_101' as input to the generator).

Probability of Disappearance (known): $\pi_{Dis} = I_T - I_G/2$

Probability of Appearance (known): $\pi_{App} = I_T + I_G/2$

Taxon Richness (known): Generated Taxon Richness.

File **Out_08 [free text].txt**; Summary Tables.

This file consists of three tables:

TAB A

-	-	Detected	Detected	Detected	Detected	Detected	Detected
		T0	T1	S T2	T3	T4	T5
Known	T0	51427	584	519	1036	222	224
Known	T1	388	297	0	7	12	0
Known	T2	313	0	246	17	0	61
Known	T3	304	14	13	1134	570	546
Known	T4	421	82	6	181	521	57
Known	T5	434	0	67	280	28	461

TAB B

-	-	Detected	Detected	Detected	Detected	Detected	Detected
		T0	T1	S T2	T3	T4	T5
Known	T0	4760.7	54.1	48	95.9	20.6	20.7
Known	T1	551.1	421.9	0	9.9	17	0
Known	T2	491.4	0	386.2	26.7	0	95.8
Known	T3	117.8	5.4	5	439.4	220.8	211.5
Known	T4	332	64.7	4.7	142.7	410.9	45
Known	T5	341.7	0	52.8	220.5	22	363

TAB C

Details		Correct answer [%]	Conditional (if a trend exists)		Uninformed Guess	Uninformed Guess Conditional
No Trend:	Type 0:	72.2			50	
A Trend Exists:	Type 1-5:	93			50	
Only Appearance	Type 1:	77.3	85.8		10	20
Only Disappearance	Type 2:	77.8	86.1		10	20
Equal Appearance and Disappearance	Type 3:	47	52.4		10	20
Appearance overwhelms Disappearance	Type 4:	59.4	61.3		10	20
Disappearance overwhelms Appearance	Type 5:	49.3	50.7		10	20
Turnover per se	Type 3:	47	52.4		10	20
Nestedness	Types 1,2:	77.5	85.9		20	40
Turnover including Richness Gradient	Types 4,5:	58.9	60.7		20	40
No Nestedness	Types 3,4,5:	87.9	93.3		30	60
Gradient	Types 1,2,4,5	76.3	81		40	80
Taxon Richness is increasing	Types 1, 4:	73.9	78.7		20	40
Taxon Richness is decreasing	Types 2,5:	72.8	77.1		20	40

Table A shows the raw numbers of sampling windows with known (rows) and detected (columns) trends.

Table B recalculates Table A into standardized numbers of various trend types. For details see the 'Settings' section.

Table C shows the probabilities of accurately estimating trends. These probabilities are calculated from Table B as follows: The total of each i-th column represents the number of sampling windows

detected with the i -th trend. The i -th cell in the i -th column indicates the number of correctly detected i -th trends. Thus, the probability is the ratio of the i -th cell to the total of the i -th column.

Conditional probabilities indicate if the trend type is accurately estimated, given a trend exists. Unconditional probabilities (first column) show the accuracy of trend type estimation, regardless of whether a trend (Type T0) exists. The 'Uninformed Guesses' represent the frequency of correctly guessing the trend type, assuming that trend-less and trend episodes occur with equal frequency.

Importantly, Table C addresses the question: 'What is the probability that an episode with a detected trend is indeed an episode with a trend?'. This means that we assess how often our analysis correctly identifies the true underlying trend when a trend is detected. However, the method does not address the reverse question: 'What is the probability that an episode with a trend is detected accurately?'. These two questions might seem similar, but they are different. The first question is about the accuracy of our detection, while the second question is about how often we can detect any trend that actually exists. To understand this difference, consider that the researcher arbitrarily claims that all episodes have a trend. Then, the answer to the second question is 100% success, but the answer to the first question depends on the actual frequency of trend episodes. These two questions have identical answers only if our detection method is 100% perfect. In real-world applications, perfect detection is rare, so it's crucial to understand this distinction to properly interpret the results of the ETA analysis.

Setting

No Trend to Trend Windows Ratio: This ratio converts Table A into Table B by specifying the number of trend-less sampling windows relative to sampling windows with a trend. For example, a 1:1 ratio results in 5,000 trend-less windows and 5,000 windows with a trend, with 1,000 windows per trend type.

Use N Windows to Assess the Match: If this option is set to "1", then detected and observed trends are considered to match each other only if there is a match between trend types in the same sampling windows. If this option is set to "3", a match between known and observed trend types is considered met if there is a match in trend types within the same or neighboring sampling windows. For example, a known sequence {... 0,1,0 ...} is accurately detected if the estimated sequence is {... 1,0,0 ...}, {... 0,1,0 ...}, {... 0,0,1 ...}, {... 1,1,0 ...}, {... 1,0,1 ...}, {... 0,1,1 ...}, or {... 1,1,1 ...}. This eliminates the effect of trend episodes not necessarily ending with the last sampling window or beginning with the first sampling window within the episode.

Utility ETA 08: Calibration

As mentioned above, the trend rates in the files 'Out_06 [free text] Control.txt', 'Out_06 [free text] UnControl.txt', 'Out_06 [free text] Combined.txt', 'Out_07 [free text] Control.txt', 'Out_07 [free text] UnControl.txt', and 'Out_07 [free text] Combined.txt' are uncalibrated and therefore cannot be compared between different data sequences. This utility is used to obtain values that are comparable between two or more sequences.

The Panel

Run:

Prepare the Calibration (The File to Calibrate data is Out_11 [free text].txt).

- (i) Load file 'Out_07 [free text].txt' from the analysis of artificial data-sequences, Utility ETA 05.
- (ii) Create file 'Out_10 [free text].txt' for simulated data.

- (iii) Set parameters on the panel (see the section 'Setting').
- (iv) Press the 'Run' button.
- (v) Create file 'Out_11 [free text].txt'
- (vi) Create file 'Out_08 [free text]'. (optional).

Calibrate Data-Sequences

(the calibration process can start from step 'vii' if the file 'Out_11' is available)

- (vii) Load 'Out_06 [free text].txt' from the analysis of the observed data-sequence.
- (viii) Load 'Out_11 [free text].txt' created in steps (i-v) above, or created earlier for data with similar ecology and taphonomy.
- (ix) Create file 'Out_10 [free text].txt' for 'real-world' data.
- (x) Press the 'Run' button.

The Files on the Input

File **Out_06 [free text].txt**: Output from Utility ETA 04 or ETA 07.

File **Out_07 [free text].txt**: Output from Utility ETA 05.

The Files on the Output

File **Out_08 [free text].txt**: Identical to the file 'Out_08' from Utility ETA 05.

File **Out_11 [free text].txt**: Internal file containing calibration data.

File **Out_10 [free text].txt**: Contains calibrated results. This file shows the same information as the loaded files Out_06 or Out_07 plus:

Trend Intensity (Calibrated Estimate): Estimated and calibrated I_T .

SD of T Intensity: Standard deviation of I_T .

SE of T Intensity: Standard error of I_T .

N for T Calibration: Number of cases used for calibration of I_T .

Gradient Intensity (Calibrated Estimate): Estimated and calibrated I_G .

SD of G Intensity: Standard deviation of I_G .

SE of G Intensity: Standard error of I_G .

N for G Calibration: Number of cases used for calibration of I_G .

Guide to the Episodic Trend Analysis (ETA) - version v0.1.0

Probability of Disappearance (Calibrated Estimate): Estimated and calibrated π_{Dis} .

Probability of Appearance (Calibrated Estimate): Estimated and calibrated π_{App} .

Trend Intensity (Adjusted): Estimated, calibrated, and adjusted I_T . Adjusted values resolve inconsistencies between raw, detected I_T and I_G and trend type. For example, raw I_T and I_G may differ from each other for detected trend T3, where the equality between intensities is expected by definition. Adjusted values of I_T and I_G are equal to each other, being consistent with T3 type. Prefer calibrated over adjusted values if possible.

Gradient Intensity (Adjusted): Estimated, calibrated and adjusted I_G .

Probability of Disappearance (Adjusted): Estimated, calibrated and adjusted π_{Dis} .

Probability of Appearance (Adjusted): Estimated, calibrated and adjusted π_{App} .

Trend Type (Adjusted): Estimated and adjusted type of the trend.

Setting

Use X % Level for Zero Probabilities: Probabilities smaller than X% of the maximum value (i.e., 1) are considered zero. Works only if the option 'Reject/accept Using 0.95/0.05 Quantiles' is unchecked.

Use X % Level for Equality of Appearance and Disappearance: Probabilities are considered equal if their difference is smaller than X% of their maximum value. Works only if the option 'Reject/accept Using 0.95/0.05 Quantiles' is unchecked.

Prefer Type 0 if Unsure: If there is uncertainty about existence of a trend during adjustment, type T0 (i.e., no trend) is assigned to the episode.

Summary Based on the Adjusted Types: If checked, the tables in 'Out_08 [free text].txt' are created using adjusted types of trends.

Set the No Trend to Trend Windows Ratio as X : Y: See setting for Utility ETA 05.

Use X Windows to Asses Match: See setting for Utility ETA 05.

Understanding Known vs Estimated Probabilities of Appearance and Disappearance

Note again that the method is designed to derive 'real' intensities and probabilities from the estimated values. Therefore, it is crucial to understand that the ETA analysis answers a question about the accuracy of the estimates. This means that ETA evaluates how well the estimated probabilities of appearance and disappearance (π_{App} and π_{Dis}) reflect the true probabilities, and the algorithm is tailored to reach an identity line between estimated values on the X-axis and 'real' values on the Y-axis.

The second question, regarding the 'frequency of accurate detection', is less relevant for our purposes. This question considers how often the actual probabilities (π_{App} and π_{Dis}) are correctly identified, which is not the primary focus of our analysis.

The distinction between these two questions is analogous to the correct interpretation of tables from file `Out_08 [free text].txt` (see the note 'Importantly, Table C addresses the question: ...').

If our estimates were 100% perfect, there would be no difference between these two questions, and the same algorithm could address both. However, since perfect estimates are rare in practice, understanding this distinction is essential for correctly interpreting the results of the ETA analysis.

FAQ

The utilities cannot be run in my computer

The dot must be set as a decimal separator in the computer.

1. Press the 'windows' and 'R' keys simultaneously
('windows' is the button on the keyboard with a picture of a window)
2. Type 'intl.cpl' in the banner and press 'enter'
3. Go to 'Additional Settings'
4. Set the 'decimal symbol' as '.' and press the 'apply' button
5. Press the 'OK' button
6. Press the 'OK' button again
7. Run the utilities

Does the Analysis Control the Episodic Trends for Global Effects (progression, retrogression)?

Yes, the Utility ETA 02 computes the global trend from the whole sequence, which is then subtracted from the particular episodic trends in Utility ETA 03. In practice, Utility ETA 03 processes the residuals of the observed T^* , N^* , $|G^*|$ from the model of the global trend given by Eqs. M3-M5.

Can the analysis run multiple times on one computer?

Yes, all the utilities can be run multiple times for several data-sequences at once. To do this, (i) create a folder, (ii) load the data and utilities into the folder, and (iii) run the analysis. Each utility opens a dialog in the folder where you loaded it and uses this folder to save the results and all temporary working files. Note that the utilities must be run one by one; otherwise, the folders may get confused with each other.

How precisely do the Utilities detect the trends in a sampling window?

In general, any year with T_i^* below the bottom limit of randomness (dashed line in Fig. 4b) is considered a year when the assemblage follows a trend (black circles in Fig. 4). However, there is a technical complexity to this method. If T_i^* is above the limit but the sum of the significances of T_i^* and N_i^* or the sum of the significances of T_i^* and G_i^* is below 2α , the trend is also considered significant. This occurs even if only the T index indicates the trend. Logically, T might be insignificant due to fluctuations, but a significant N or G can also indicate a trend (while insignificant N or G do not indicate the absence of a trend).

This feature can be switched on or off at the bottom left-side panel of Utility ETA 04.

Can one introduce specific expert knowledge on the analyzed sequence into the analysis?

Yes, the method is designed to **incorporate** expert knowledge. If the researcher is confident about trend-free periods (e.g., stable climate, absence of charcoal, or absence of archaeological finds may indicate the absence of forces driving trends in assemblages in some episodes), then the range of randomness can be estimated from this knowledge, refining the results. However, it is important to assume that these expert-identified, trend-less episodes are representative of the sequence and do not bias the values of T^* . Expert knowledge is introduced into the analysis via file In_04 and Utility ETA 02.

Why do probabilities slightly differ between two analyses of the same data?

There are random procedures implemented in fitting distributions and models where an analytical approach is not available or is difficult. These irregularities, however, do not affect the overall results of the analysis.

How to set Quantiles for Data-Specific Limits of Range of Randomness?

The limits of ranges of randomness determine the significance of Turnover, Nestedness and Gradient for each sampling window. When T^* and N^* are below their respective limits (dashed horizontal lines in Fig. 4 in Šizling et al., 202X), then Turnover and Nestedness are significant. When G^* is below its lower limit or above its upper limit, then Gradient is significant. These limits are based on the quantile of the alpha level set on the panel and the Student's or Laplace frequency distribution, which fit the index values of large open circles in Fig. 4. (See the panel to switch between Student and Laplace distributions.) Users can set the alpha levels of thresholds to, e.g., 0.05. Note, however, that the quantile is not a true significance level since we are not testing a hypothesis but sorting changes according to their randomness. The most effective alpha level we tested was,

$$\alpha = 1/(2n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + 1). \quad \text{Eq. M7}$$

Here n_1 and n_2 are the numbers of sampling windows where $r_{i,T,p}^* > 0$ and $r_{i,T,p}^* = 0$, respectively. For T^* and N^* , the number n_3 is the number of sampling windows with $r_{T,p}^* < 0$ and $T^* > 0$, respectively. For G^* , the number $n_3 = 0$ because both upper and lower limits are needed in this case. The Eq. M7 alpha level corresponds to the T^* , N^* values of the lowest large open circle, and G^* values of the lowest and highest large open circles if the distribution of large open circles were perfect. This choice of alpha level eliminates the fluctuations of the large open circles. Setting alpha values to 0 on the Utility_04 panel activates this option.

Our empirical experience with pollen data shows little difference between the performance of the Student's t and Laplace distributions, with the Student's t distribution performing slightly better.

What if the minimum and maximum depth of sampling windows is unknown?

This issue affects the process of calibration. In the analysis of a timeline, the spans of sampling windows are defined in years (In_01). In simulations, the time spans of sampling windows are implemented via the upper and lower depths of each sampling windows and depth age model. This may not be suitable for palaeontological or archaeological data, where the minimum and maximum ages are directly attributed to each sampling window.

Solution: (i) replace 'Depths in cm' with the years in Sampling Scheme (In_104), and in the depth-age model (In_102). This means that the columns 'Depth' and 'Age' will be identical. See also Figures in the 'Setting' section for Utility ETA 04 above.

What if neither the minimum and maximum depth nor the minimum and maximum ages of sampling windows are known?

In this case, we cannot control for the span of sampling window (τ , Fig. 1).

Solution: (i) replace the span of the sampling window in the file 'In_01' with any integer; (ii) replace 'Depth' in the Depth-Age model (In_102) with Years, so that the columns 'Depth' and 'Age' are identical); (iii) replace 'Min Depths' and 'Max Depths' in Sampling Scheme with middle year of the sampling window, making the columns 'Min Depths' and 'Max Depths' identical; (iv) switch off the option 'Include Spans of Sampling Windows' on the panel of Utility ETA 02.

What if there is no information on the numbers of sampled specimens?

Solution: (i) replace the number of sampled specimens with any integer in all files; (ii) switch off the option 'Include N of Sampled Specimens' on the panel of the Utility_02; (iii-a) switch off the option 'Involve sampling effect ...' on the panel of Utility ETA 101; or (iii-b) follow the instructions in Setting section for an alternative to loading the file 'In_103' into the utility_101.

What if there is information on the total number of sampled specimens for each sampling window, but the number of sampled specimens for particular species is unknown?

Solution: (i) replace the number of 'Sampled Specimens' in the file In_03 with any nonzero integer. (ii) the user may choose to switch off or leave on the option 'Include N of Sampled Specimens' on the panel of Utility ETA 02.

If the option 'Include N of Sampled Specimens' is switched on, the test assumes that all taxa are sampled with equal probability, as if there were no rare and common taxa.

How does the analysis work for sequences without trend-free episodes or sequences without a trend episode?

There is always a possibility that a trend occurs over the entire sequence, or that there is no trend at all. Unlike the common statistical methods, the method can handle both cases. In the first case, there are no sampling windows with $r_{i,T}^* > 0$, the standard deviation (SD) is zero, and all sampling windows are attributed to a trend. In the second case, the magnitude of randomness covers all sampling windows, and none of the sampling windows are attributed to a trend.

Can the method detect Trends shorter than the three sampling windows period?

When the trend period falls between a triplet of sampling windows, the triplet is only partially affected by the trend, and the trend may or may not be detected. Therefore, if a trend is detected in the data, it should be assumed that the trend may not occur exactly in the identified sampling window but is likely somewhere around or between the detected windows. The longer the period with a trend, the more likely it is that a trend will be detected in at least one sampling window near the trend period.

Why does only one taxon appear or disappear in each step of the simulation?

We run simulations so that no more than one taxon disappears and appears in the assemblage each year. The probabilities of disappearance and appearance are then defined as the frequencies of these events. This definition is driven by practical issues, ensuring that equal probabilities lead to a long-term zero gradient in taxon richness. However, we do not expect only one taxon to appear or disappear from a real assemblage per time unit (e.g., year, Myr, etc.) or spatial unit (e.g., km). It is possible that multiple taxa appear or disappear during one time (or spatial) unit and none during another.

The sequence of assemblages is sampled with sampling windows that span multiple units (see Fig. 1). Our simulation method, combined with sampling using these windows, therefore mimics both gradual and rapid episodic changes in assemblages. Another advance of this definition is that the probabilities can be interpreted in terms of the period during which one species appears or disappears (e.g. if $\pi_{App} = 0.1$ and time unit is Ky, then one species appears on average per $1/0.1=10$ kilo years; or if the unit is km, in spatial transects, then one species appears on average per 10 kilometres).